

PREPARATION OF 2-ARYLAMINO-4-(2-THIENYL)-THIAZOLES AND THEIR AZO AND MERCURATED DERIVATIVES

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Twelve new 2-arylamino-4-(2-thienyl)-thiazoles have been prepared by the condensation of different substituted thioureas with 2-thienylmethyl ketone and coupled with diazotised sulphanilamide. As expected, the sulphonamidophenylazo group enters the thiazole nucleus at position-5 in support of which some decisive evidences have also been stated. The thiazole compounds have been mercurated and the mercurated products tested for their bactericidal and fungicidal actions. Fungicidal results of the mercurated compounds are quite promising.

In view of the fact that antibiostaminic properties are exhibited in a pronounced manner by both thiazolylamines and thiophene compounds (Saijo, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1952, 72, 1009; Dahlbom, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1950, 4, 744; Friduan, *Zhur. Obshchei Khim.*, 1953, 23, 278; Kyrides *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 745), an investigation on the preparation of some thiazole compounds containing a thiophene moiety was undertaken with the object of testing the compounds for the above properties as well as for other biological effects. Twelve compounds of this series have been prepared by condensing 2-thienylmethyl ketone with different N-substituted monoaryl thioureas in presence of iodine according to our method reported earlier (*this Journal*, 1953, 30, 398). These thiazole derivatives have been characterised by their acetyl and picrate derivatives.

The recent interesting uses of azo dyes as powerful disinfectants (Ostromislensky, U. S. Pat. 1, 785, 327/1930) as insecticides in controlling European torn borer and for use on spider mite and Mexican beetle (Questel *et al.*, U.S. Dept. Agr. Bur. Entom. and PLT Quar., 1941, p. 557; Eddy and Carson, *J. Econ. Entom.*, 1946, 39, 631) and as effective antiviral agents (Ueda *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1952, 72, 1343), encouraged us to undertake the preparation of some azo derivatives of the above thiazole compounds. Since the azo derivatives derived from sulphanilamide produce the maximum of these effects, specially as antiviral agents (Hiyama, *ibid.*, 1952, 72, 1374), these azo dyes have been prepared by coupling 2-aryl-substituted-amino-4-(2-thienyl)-thiazoles with diazotised sulphanilamide.

On the basis of earlier observations (Beyer and Wolter, *Chem. Ber.*, 1952, 85, 1077; Erlenmeyer *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1942, 25, 1066; Ganapathi and Venkataraman, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 22A, 348), it has been assumed that the azophenylsulphonamido group enters the thiazole nucleus and attaches to the C₅ position. The possibility of the azo group being linked to the aryl nucleus, attached to the amino group at C₂, is completely excluded by the fact that when the azo compound, prepared from diazotised sulphanilamide and 2-phenylamino-4-(2-thienyl)-thiazole, is reduced with sodium hydrosulphite, the resulting product containing a free amino group (m.p. 166°; found: N, 14.93; S, 23.42; C₁₃H₁₁N₃S₂, requiring N, 15.38; S, 23.47%) is not identical with 2-(*p*)-aminophenylamino-4-(2-thienyl)-thiazole (m.p. 123°; N, 15.11; S, 23.40;

$C_{13}H_{11}N_2S_2$ requiring N, 15.38 ; S, 23.47%) which is obtained from *p*-aminophenylthiourea and 2-thienylmethyl ketone by the usual procedure, reported earlier. The substitution of the hydrogen atom of the thiophene nucleus by the azo group is also ruled out on the following considerations.

It has been reported by Beyer and Wolter (*loc. cit.*) that when 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole is coupled with benzenediazonium chloride, the azophenyl group does not attach to the phenyl nucleus at the carbon atom 4. It has also been reported by one of us (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 690) that when 2-amino-4-(2-thienyl)-thiazole is coupled with diazotised sulphanilamide, the azo group does not attach to the thiophene group at C₄, but to the C₅ of the thiazole nucleus. From this observation it may be concluded that the azo group does not go to the thiophene nucleus. Further support in favour of the azo group entering C₅ of the thiazole nucleus is afforded by the inability of 4:5-disubstituted-2-arylaminothiazoles of undergoing coupling with diazotised sulphanilamide, as reported earlier (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 933).

The thiazole compounds, prepared above, have also been mercurated with mercuric acetate with the formation of acetoxymercuri compounds to substantially augment the bactericidal as well as fungicidal activities of the thiazoles (cf. Das, Mahapatra and Rout, *ibid.*, 1955, 32, 55 ; Rout *et al.*, *Nature*, 1954, 174, 516). It has been assumed on the basis of the earlier work (Rout *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 4057 ; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, 13B, 378) that the acetoxymercuri group enters the aryl nucleus attached to the amino group at C₂, at the *para*-position (with respect to -NH group) of the aryl nucleus and that if the *para*-position is blocked, the substitution occurs at the *ortho*-position. When the mercurated derivative of 4-(2-thienyl)-2-phenylaminothiazole is treated with bromine water or potassium perbromate solution, the acetoxymercuri group is knocked off, and is replaced by a bromine atom and the identity of this compound (m.p. 106° ; Br, 23.43 ; S, 18.45 ; $C_{13}H_9N_2BrS_2$ requiring Br 23.74 ; S, 18.98%) with 2-(*p*)-bromophenylamino-4-(2-thienyl)-thiazole (m.p. 107° ; Br, 23.31 ; S, 18.63 ; $C_{13}H_9N_2S_2Br$ requiring Br, 23.74, S, 18.98%) prepared from *p*-bromophenylthiourea and 2-thienylmethyl ketone lends decisive support in favour of the aryl nucleus undergoing mercuration. In case the aryl nucleus happens to be α - or β -naphthyl groups, the acetoxymercuri group enters the nucleus according to the rule of substitution in the naphthalene compounds.

The experimental procedures adopted for the preparation of thiazoles, their azo dyes and mercurated compounds have been illustrated with one example in each case in the Experimental.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Monoaryl-substituted Thioureas.—The phenyl-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-tolyl-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-chlorophenyl-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-carboxyphenyl-, α - and β -naphthyl-thioureas have been synthesised by the methods discussed earlier.

4-(2-Thienyl)-2-phenylaminothiazole.—A mixture containing phenylthiourea (6 g., 2 M), 2-thienylmethyl ketone (2.5 g., 1 M) and iodine (1 M) was heated under reflux for 12 hours on a water-bath and again for 12 hours after removal of the condenser. The deeply coloured crude reaction product was kept in contact with ether for 48 hours

with occasional shaking to remove the excess of iodine as well as the unchanged ketone. The ether was decanted off and the reaction product was kept in contact with a dilute solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ for half an hour with occasional stirring. The resulting product was boiled with water to remove any unchanged thioureas. The residue was then treated with concentrated ammonium hydroxide, when a gummy product was obtained which did not solidify even on keeping in contact with ammonia for 4 days. The gummy product was made solid by converting it first to a solid picrate and subsequently decomposing the picrate with LiOH solution and extracting the desired compound with ether, yield 63%, m.p. 146° . (Found: N, 10.15; S, 24.13. Compound requires N, 10.95; S, 24.80%).

Thiazoles obtained from carboxyphenylthioureas were soluble in concentrated ammonia and were separated by acidifying carefully the ammoniacal solution with acetic acid. The thiazole bases were acetylated by heating them with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine for about half an hour. The analytical data and properties of the thiazoles, their picrates and their acetyl derivatives are shown in Table I.

2-Phenylamino-4-(2-thienyl)-5-azophenyl-(p)-sulphonamidothiazole.—Sulpanilamide (0.8 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (2 c.c.) and diluted with water to 100 c.c. and diazotised with NaNO_2 (0.5 g. dissolved in 30 c.c. water) dropwise (until starch iodide showed an excess of HNO_2) in an ice-bath with efficient mechanical stirring. The resulting diazo solution being buffered with 10 g. of sodium acetate was added gradually with stirring to a previously well-cooled solution of 2-phenylamino-4-(2-thienyl)-thiazole (1 g. dissolved in 2 c.c. of acetic acid diluted to 40 c.c. with water), kept in an ice-bath. The reaction product was then stirred for another hour, when the orange-red azo dye separated out. This was collected by filtration and finally crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 181° , yield 71%. (Found: N, 15.96; S, 21.13. Compound requires N, 15.87; S, 21.77%). The properties and analytical data of the azo dyes are shown in Table II.

Mercuration of the Thiazoles.—To the thiazole compound (1 M), dissolved in alcohol-acetic acid solution, a solution of mercuric acetate (1.3 M) in water, acidified with dilute acetic acid, was added. Precipitate appeared in some cases after a while. The reaction mixture was kept overnight, filtered and washed thoroughly with hot water, dilute alcohol and finally with very dilute acetic acid. The properties and analytical data of the mercurated compounds are recorded in Table IV.

Bactericidal test.—The Ridcal-Walker Serial Drop Dilution method was used for the comparative antibacterial activity. The bactericidal activity was measured in terms of maximum effective dilution (M.E.D.) of the thiazoles, their azo dyes and the mercurated thiazoles at 10 minutes' contact. The test organisms used were 24 hours' culture of *E. coli* and *Staph. aureus*. The mercurated compounds exhibited a very high activity, some of them being active in more than 1 : 80,000 dilution. The bactericidal data of the compounds are recorded in Table III.

TABLE I

No. of compound.	Nature of the aryl group R	2-Arylamino 4-(2-thienyl)thiazole.			Picrate derivative.			Acetyl derivative.					
		M.P.	Yield.	%Nitrogen.	%Sulphur.	M.P.	Yield.	%Sulphur.	M.P.	Yield.	%Sulphur		
		Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.		
1	Ph.	146°	63%	10.15	10.85	24.13	24.80	14.09	13.14	171°	90%	21.89	21.33
2	<i>o</i> -Tol.	150°	71	10.82	10.79	23.83	23.53	12.13	12.77	118°	89	20.87	20.38
3	<i>m</i> -Tol.	131°	78	10.67	10.49	24.19	23.53	12.81	12.77	141°	87	20.13	20.38
4	<i>p</i> -Tol.	167°	67	10.43	10.29	24.31	23.53	13.61	12.77	146°	81	19.89	20.38
5	(<i>o</i>)-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	109°	59	9.01	9.57	22.10	21.88	11.89	12.27	98°	83	18.79	19.13
6	(<i>m</i>)-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	142°	63	8.78	9.57	21.31	21.88	12.71	12.27	137°	78	20.11	19.13
7	(<i>p</i>)-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	211°	61	10.13	9.57	21.19	21.88	12.59	12.27	181°	75	19.78	19.13
8	(<i>o</i>)-COOH-C ₆ H ₄	209°	65	9.11	9.27	20.89	21.19	12.74	12.05	217°	71	19.51	18.60
9	(<i>m</i>)-COOH-C ₆ H ₄	205°	71	9.80	9.27	21.87	21.19	11.91	12.05	219°	83	17.87	18.60
10	(<i>p</i>)-COOH-C ₆ H ₄	216°	71	9.71	9.27	21.10	21.19	11.25	12.05	209°	76	18.13	18.60
11	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	122°	85	8.79	9.00	21.11	20.78	11.13	11.91	256°	93	18.81	18.28
12	β -C ₁₀ H ₇	225° (decomp.)	87	9.79	9.00	20.36	20.78	12.51	11.91	245°d	91	18.70	18.28

TABLE II

2-Arylamino-4-(2-thienyl)-5-azophenyl-(p)-sulfonamidothiazole.

*No. of compound.	M. P.	Yield.	Colour of the azo dye.	%Sulphur.		%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1	181°	71%	Orange-red	21.13	21.77	15.96	15.87
2	148°	67	Yellow	21.11	21.09	15.81	15.38
3	168°	63	Orange yellow	20.89	21.09	14.75	15.38
4	144°	69	Dirty yellow	20.67	21.09	14.96	15.38
5	111°	59	Red	20.75	20.18	15.01	14.72
6	104°	65	Brownish-red	20.31	20.18	14.37	14.72
7	135°	71	Yellow	19.87	20.18	14.92	14.72
8	112°	53	Chocolate	18.99	19.79	14.79	14.43
9	261°	55	Chocolate	19.13	19.79	14.85	14.43
10	249°	59	Chocolate-red	19.63	19.79	13.79	14.43
11	158°	75	Chocolate	20.18	19.55	14.78	14.25
12	184°	85	Chocolate	20.34	19.55	14.61	14.25

* Nature of the aryl group R corresponds to those in Table I (column 2)

TABLE III

Bactericidal activity.						Fungicidal activity.			
No. of comp. (vide Table I)	M. E. D.		No. of comp. (vide Table II)	M. I. D.		No. of comp. (vide Table IV)	M. E. D.	No. of comp. (vide Table IV)	No. germi- nation (ln p p m).
	E. Coli.	Staph. Aureus.		E. Coli.	Staph. Aureus.				
1	1:2000	1:4000	1	1:1000	1:2000	1	1:40000	1	9
2	1:2000	1:4000	2	1:1000	1:2000	2	1:20000	2	9
3	1:2000	1:4000	3	1:1000	1:2000	3	1:20000	3	9
4	1:2000	1:4000	4	1:1000	1:2000	4	1:20000	4	9
5	1:2000	1:4000	5	1:1000	1:4000	5	1:40000	5	8
6	1:2000	1:4000	6	1:1000	1:4000	6	1:40000	6	8
7	1:2000	1:4000	7	1:1000	1:2000	7	1:40000	7	8
8	1:1000	1:1000	8	<1:1000	1:2000	8	1:20000	8	12
9	1:1000	1:1000	9	<1:1000	1:2000	9	1:20000	9	11
10	1:1000	1:1000	10	<1:1000	1:2000	10	1:20000	10	13
11	1:2000	1:4000	11	1:2000	1:4000	11	1:80000	11	8
12	1:2000	1:4000	12	1:1000	1:4000	12	1:80000	12	8

TABLE IV

No. of the comp.	Nature of the group R'.	M. P.	Yield.	%Mercury.	
				Found.	Calc.
1	-C ₆ H ₄ -	235°	71%	37.93	38.75
2	-(o)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -	192°	65	37.81	37.73
3	-(m)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -	226°	69	36.95	37.73
4	-(p)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -	291°	75	37.15	37.73
5	-(o)Cl-C ₆ H ₃ -	278°	73	35.78	36.33
6	-(m)Cl-C ₆ H ₃ -	204°	78	36.53	36.33
7	-(p)Cl-C ₆ H ₃ -	217°	76	36.81	36.33
8	-(o)COOH-C ₆ H ₃ -	275°	61	35.13	35.71
9	-(m)COOH-C ₆ H ₃ -	>350°	63	35.51	35.71
10	-(p)COOH-C ₆ H ₃ -	>350°	59	35.93	35.71
11	-(α)-C ₁₀ H ₆ -	241°	86	34.91	35.33
12	-(β)-C ₁₀ H ₆ -	255°	89	35.93	35.33

Fungicidal Tests.—For fungicidal assay, the spore germination method of Montgomery and Moore (*J. Pomol. & Hort. Sci.*, 1938, 15, 553) with a slight modification has been used. *Piricularia orizae*, Cav. was used as the test fungus. The mercurated thiazoles are not very active as fungicides; only 100 p.p.m. is active in inhibiting the spore germination. The mercurated compounds showed a high activity, being 100% effective in inhibiting the spore germination of the fungus at a concentration of 8 p.p.m., and at 3 p.p.m. the spore germination being 50% only. The data of the fungicidal test are recorded in Table III.

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